

Promoting Inclusive Education to Boost Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Catalyst for Attainment of Sustainable Development Goals

Victor Ugochukwu Ezeonwumelu , Ugochukwu Ifeyinwa Offor, PhD,
Mary Nneka Nwikpo, PhD , Chukwuma Martins Onunkwo,
Patricia Ego Nwaru
*Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria*

Abstract

This paper explores the pivotal role of inclusive education in nurturing entrepreneurial intentions among individuals, consequently contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals. Entrepreneurship is increasingly recognized as a driving force behind economic growth, job creation, and innovation. Therefore, equipping individuals with the necessary skills and mindset to become successful entrepreneurs is of paramount importance and a prerequisite for a nation's sustainable development. Inclusive education ensures that individuals from diverse backgrounds, irrespective of their socio-economic status, gender, ethnicity, or disabilities, are provided with equitable opportunities to learn, grow, and explore their entrepreneurial potential. By embracing inclusive education, educational institutions can create an environment that promotes diversity and fosters entrepreneurial qualities such as creativity, risk-taking, problem-solving, and adaptability. Through inclusive programmes, students are exposed to diverse perspectives, enabling them to develop an entrepreneurial mien which could be a panacea for emancipation from unemployment. This paper concedes that inclusive education plays a crucial role in eliminating barriers that marginalized groups face in accessing quality education. Thus, to empower individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds to become active contributors to their communities and economies, there is need for leveraging inclusive education initiatives as societies can tap into the untapped potential of budding entrepreneurs, leading to greater economic productivity and social welfare. The impetus for promoting inclusive education to boost entrepreneurial intentions aligns closely with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined by the United Nations. Inclusive education supports SDG 4 (Quality Education) by ensuring equitable access to education and fostering lifelong learning opportunities. Additionally, it intertwines with SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) by cultivating an entrepreneurial ecosystem that generates opportunities, creates employment, and promotes economic development. To achieve these, the following recommendations were made that there is cogent need for improved advocacy for inclusive funding opportunities for those that are disadvantaged. In addition to that, policies that encourage vulnerable persons' active involvement in entrepreneurial training and ventures should be encouraged.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Keywords: *Unemployment, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Sustainable Development, Inclusive Education.*

Suggested citation: Ezeonwumelu, V.U., Offor, U.I., Nwikpo, M.N., Onunkwo, C.M, & Nwaru, P.E. (2025). Promoting Inclusive Education to Boost Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Catalyst for Attainment of Sustainable Development Goals. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(1), 65-76. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(1).06

Introduction

Unemployment is a scourge that has refused to be tossed aside despite the lofty promises and proclamations made by politicians on their route to political power. In Nigeria, the unemployment rate is pegged at a horrendous 33% (National Bureau Statistics, 2023). To make an already terrible situation worse, a leading global financials' consulting firm reported that unemployment rate in Nigeria will hit 41% by the end of 2023 (Channels TV, 2023). This implies that if something drastic is not done in the nearest future, unemployment is about to become an epidemic in Nigeria.

Several undesirable behaviours, vices and social maladies have been linked to unemployment. High poverty rate, crime, corruption and youth restiveness (Egbewole *et al.*, 2021; Osuji, Ekham & Tony-Okolo, 2021; Nelson & Ayawei, 2020; Wada, 2018). When individuals, mostly in their youthful and productive ages do not have any means of livelihood, they tend to engage in behaviours that are inimical to national development. To put this into context, national development entails improvement in various indices that point to the betterment of the lives of the people. Thus, high unemployment will definitely inhibit national development.

National development is considered a desideratum for many nations. Every nation hope that the country attains several milestones that place the said nation on a pedestal reserved for countries that have excelled in the several indices that predict progress. National development has been defined as the degree of success a nation experiences in providing a source of livelihood for its teeming population. Orji and Job (2013) added that some of the indices involved in measuring national development include, elimination of poverty, providing food for the masses and providing access to basic and social amenities.

Sustainable development is simply defined as “development that meets the needs of the present, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Sustainable Development Commission nd: 1). Sustainable development entails much more than tangible development that can be measured using socioeconomic indices that centers around wealth and lack of resources. Mensah (2018) claimed that sustainable development discussions in contemporary times and provides a framework for studying the interplay of human and natural resources in shaping the physical and social environment for generations yet unborn. Sustainable development entails egalitarianism, a system that promotes equity and inclusivity. Ametepeyi *et al.* (2023) argued that the principles of sustainable development is soldered to intergenerational justice which must reflect on the conservation of resources as well as the distribution of opportunities. Inclusive education promotes the principles of equity and social

justice. By providing equal educational opportunities to all students, regardless of their abilities or socio-economic realities, inclusive education helps to build a more just and inclusive society for future generations.

To bridge the employment gap that continues to threaten the very fabric of our national existence, it is time to look outside the box for solutions. With the persistent pressure on our overstretched labour market the onus to create jobs and push millions of young Nigerians out of abject poverty now rest on the job seeking individuals. The concept of entrepreneurship has been promoted as a probable solution to unemployment in Nigeria (Ezeonwumelu *et al.*, 2022; Olufemi, 2020). Entrepreneurship involves the employment of human skills and innovative ideas to create value and functional solutions to various societal problems. Entrepreneurship is predicted by several factors ranging from self-efficacy to entrepreneurial intentions. Adesunkammi and Oyolola (2023) defined entrepreneurial intention as the desire to apply one's know-how in a bid to accomplish problem-solving tasks that are directed at creating value. Thus, entrepreneurial intention is central to the success of any entrepreneurial venture (Adesunkammi & Oyolola, 2023; Ezeonwumelu *et al.*, 2022).

In today's rapidly evolving global landscape, the pursuit of sustainable development has become more critical than ever. As nations strive to cultivate vibrant economies and socially inclusive societies, the role of education has emerged as a catalyst for achieving these goals. Particularly, the concept of inclusive education holds immense potential for fostering entrepreneurial intentions, thus driving both social and economic progress. This opinion paper delves into the importance of promoting inclusive education as a means to ignite and nurture entrepreneurial aspirations, ultimately propelling Nigeria towards attaining sustainable development.

Sustainable Development Goals: An overview

The history of the sustainable development goals, SDGs can be traced back to the United Nation's Rio-20 conference held in Brazil in 2012. At the conference, world leaders strategized on policies that would produce a more robust template than the Millenium Development Goals, MDGs which was set to expire in 2015. Following extensive consultation and negotiates the SDGs were adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in September 2015 as part of the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. Alamu (2017) claimed that the SDGs aim to address a wide range of social, economic and environmental challenges faced by countries around the world, with a focus on eradicating poverty, promoting equality and preserving the planet.

According to the United Nation's 193 member states, as captured in the Food and Agricultural Organisation, FAO, the seventeen (17) sustainable development goal, include,

1. End poverty in all its form everywhere.
2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all age.
4. Ensure inclusive and equitable education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.
5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.

6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation of life.
7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.
8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
10. Reduce inequality within and among countries.
11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.
12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.
15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
16. Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.
17. Strengthening the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.
18. These goals were designed to be interconnected, recognizing the importance of addressing multiple dimensions of sustainable development simultaneously.

Boosting Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Panacea for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

In the face of the soaring unemployment and outrageous cost of living in Nigeria, advocacy for entrepreneurial intentions appeals to be a no-brainer. This is because entrepreneurship appears to hold the promise of creating employment opportunities, driving innovation, and fostering economic growth in the country. Ezech and Nkamnebe (2019) argued that entrepreneurial intentions explain engagement in entrepreneurship-oriented ventures and bodes well for the advancement of national values. Boosting entrepreneurial intentions can indeed play a crucial role fostering sustainable development in Nigeria. This can be achieved through entrenching positive outcomes associated with entrepreneurship. Some of these outcomes that precipitate sustainable development are;

Economic Diversification

As a nation that has traditionally relied on oil and allied hydrocarbons for decades, the Nigerian economy is highly dependent on forex from crude. Encouraging entrepreneurial intention stimulates other sectors of the economy from crude sale. Nkuda (2021) rightly affirmed that economic diversification is a right step towards attainment of sustainable development and is contingent on the availability of policies that create a suitable environment for young entrepreneurs to thrive.

Job Creation

There is no gains aging the fact that enhanced entrepreneurial intentions provides more jobs and drastically reduces unemployment. Entrepreneurship leads to the creation of new business and startup ventures. These enterprises require a workforce, employs same and reduce the number of unemployed people loitering the streets.

Innovation and Technology

Innovation is the hallmark of creativity. Law and Breznik (2016) identified innovation as a creative purveyor of entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurs introduce innovative ideas and technologies to the market. This innovation triggers improved productivity and competitiveness, which are necessary for long-term economic growth.

Resource Utilisation

Nigeria is blessed with vast natural resources. Entrepreneurial intentions make it possible for the birthing of ideas that can help facilitate the efficient utilization of these resources, thereby promoting sustainability and reducing wastage.

Access to Finance

Entrepreneurial intentions, when properly harnessed can help in fostering a robust financial ecosystem. In nations renowned for creating value and harnessing innovative ideas boasts of avenues through which young creative minds can access funds to finance their various startups. Onyekwelu *et al.* (2023) asserted that entrepreneurship boosts sustainability by providing young startups with access to finance as a result of the multiplier effect of the positive financial indices stimulated by increased productivity.

Social Impact

Entrepreneurial intentions is central to addressing social issues that hinge on inequality, exclusion and deprivation. Thus, entrepreneurship can help provide solutions to problems such as access to healthcare, clean energy and education. Social entrepreneurship in this context can contribute to sustainable development goals.

Global Opportunities

By entrenching entrepreneurial intentions, there is a chance that entrepreneurship opens doors to global market. Nigerian entrepreneurs can tap into international markets, boosting exports and attracting foreign investment. This is inadvertently a precursor to creating a stable and robust economy, consequently leading to Nigeria's attainment of SDGs.

Fostering entrepreneurial intentions is a multi-faceted approach to achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. It not only contributes to economic growth but also addresses social and environmental challenges, making it a promising panacea for the nation's attainment of SDGs.

Inclusive Education and Sustainable Development

Inclusive education is a philosophy and approach to education that strives to provide equal access and opportunities to all learners irrespective of their socio-economic realities, abilities, or disabilities. Obi and Mary (2016) advocated for inclusive education to be adopted at all levels of the Nigerian education system, claiming that it promotes

developmentally appropriate practice that leads to positive learning and socio-emotional outcomes. Kusimo and Chidozie (2019) scrutinized inclusive education in Nigeria in the framework of Sustainable Development Goals, pointing out the need to adopt policies that cater for the very vulnerable in the society.

A cursory look at the SDGs highlights the primary attached to making education accessible to, and by all, irrespective of the individual's peculiarities. Persons with disabilities, as well as indigent learners are often categorized as vulnerable and susceptible to denial of access to education. Dare and Dare (2018) reported that adequate provisions should be made for this class of learners if they are to benefit from instruction. Assistance, usually in the form of social support and instructional aids have been found to be of help to teachers when working with special needs learners, as well as indigent students. The Alliance for Inclusive Education asserted that inclusive education is the basis of lifelong equality and is built on principles that include:

The Right to Education

Every individual has the right to quality education without discrimination.

Equal Opportunities

inclusive education ensures that all students have equal access to educational resources, facilities and support services.

Individualized Learning

Inclusive education recognized and accommodates the diverse learning needs and styles of students, providing support and adapting teaching method accordingly.

Collaboration and Cooperation

Inclusive educations promotes collaboration among students, teachers, parents and the wider community, fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

Respect for Diversity

Inclusive education respects the diverse cultures, languages, abilities and backgrounds of students, celebrating their unique identities.

The intersection of inclusive education and sustainable development lies in the belief that education is a fundamental right and a veritable tool for promoting social inclusion, equity and sustainable development. Inclusive education plays a crucial role in ensuring that all individuals, including those from marginalized groups, have access to quality education enabling them to actively participate in society and contribute to sustainable development efforts.

Inclusive Education Strategies for Stimulating Entrepreneurial Intentions

Promoting inclusive education and fostering entrepreneurial intentions are crucial elements for achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs). Inclusive education strategies can play a significant role in empowering individuals, including vulnerable persons, to develop entrepreneurial skills and contribute to sustainable development. here are some strategies for stimulating entrepreneurial intentions through inclusive education:

Providing Equal Access to Education

Talent alone is never enough to predict success in any given endeavour. There is need for proper nurturing if talent is to yield the desired end products that culminate in problem solving feats and solutions. It is vital that young individuals are provided with equal access to inclusive education. Nzegbulem and Odinonye (2016) decried the obvious gaps that exist as regards learners' access to entrepreneurial education in Nigeria. This gap can be plugged by removing barriers such as gender inequality, disability discrimination, socioeconomic disparities and cultural biases. Every individual should have an opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills necessary for entrepreneurship, irrespective of their background.

Incorporate Entrepreneurship Education into the Curriculum

Incorporating entrepreneurship education into the curriculum at all levels is essential. Ezeonwumelu and Okoro (2021) made a case for integrating entrepreneurship education at all levels of our educational sector to reduce unemployment and enhance national development. Teaching entrepreneurial skills such as creativity, critical thinking, problem-solving, risk assessment and communication are vital to fostering entrepreneurial intentions. In providing entrepreneurship education, there is need for emphasis to be placed on both theoretical knowledge and practical experience. Yang (2017) posited that integration of practice in the teaching of entrepreneurial skills enriches learning experience. Case studies, business simulations and modelling are very important experiences that are vital in entrepreneurship education.

Integrating Experiential Learning

Providing opportunities for experiential learning is necessary for stimulating entrepreneurial intentions. This can be achieved through internships, apprenticeships, business incubators, mentorship programmes and collaboration with firms within the locality. Motta and Galina (2023) explained that experiential learning is an ideal pedagogical approach as it allows students to learn by doing. Thus, experiential learning allows students to gain practical insights, develop networks and apply their entrepreneurial skills in real life situations.

Employing Desirable Models

According to renowned psychologist, Albert Bandura, learners have tendency to copy behaviour exhibited by models. Using observational learning to explain how attitudes, behaviour and emotional expressions are acquired, Bandura hinted that student learn by observing what happens around them. Introducing vulnerable students to successful entrepreneurs particularly those from minority or disadvantaged groups is encouraged. Role models and their success stories inspire the students to understand that entrepreneurship is accessible to everyone regardless of possible disability or any other form of vulnerability.

Encouraging Collaboration and Networking

Inclusive education should encourage collaboration and networking among students, educators' entrepreneurs and other stakeholders from the community. It is essential that every learner, irrespective of the learner's peculiarities is granted access to opportunities that stem from astute networking. Magni and Mazzina (2018) asserted that collaboration bodes well for entrepreneurial intentions as it encourages resource sharing, creates a social exchange space and entrenches mutual cooperation. Vulnerable individuals should be availed this opportunity which helps them expand their network, improving their chances of attaining success. There is need for

collaborative projects, team-based activities and networking events. These provide opportunities for vulnerable students to build relationships, develop a sense of belonging, share ideas and learn from each other, such collaborations can foster a supportive environment for entrepreneurial intentions to blossom.

Building a Supportive Ecosystem

Establishing a supportive ecosystem is crucial for inclusive education strategies to work. This involves engaging various stakeholders such as government agencies, educational institutions, businesses, NGOs and communities. Collaboration between these stakeholders can create an enabling environment that offers financial support, mentorship, legal frameworks and infrastructure for aspiring entrepreneurs.

Addressing Gender Disparities

Inclusive education strategies must address gender disparities in entrepreneurship. Bearing in mind that inclusive education entails equity it is justified that proportionate considerations are factored into the designing and implementation of entrepreneurship curricula. Pimpa (2021) implied that women already stand at a disadvantage, juggling family expectations personal life and a skewed cultural disposition towards certain gender-based ventures. These challenges faced by women are compounded by limited access to resources, cultural biases and lack of network. To plug this apparent gap, specific programmes should be implemented to empower, and support women entrepreneurs, providing mentorship opportunities and promoting gender equality can help address these disparities. Some notable programmes that have yielded results in the past in Nigeria include, Women Empowerment Programme and Scheme Synergy, WEPSS, Women for Women International, African Women Power Network, Well Being Foundation, etc. it is pertinent that these considerations are made to accommodate women with entrepreneurial intentions.

Individualised Support and Accommodations

Inclusive education for entrepreneurship requires providing individualized support and accommodations for students with disabilities or special needs. This may include assistive technology, additional time task completion. Support from inclusion specialists or learning support staff.

Employing Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

UDL is a teaching method that aims to provide multiple means of representation, expression and engagement to address the diverse needs and interests of learners. Dalton (2017) opined that the UDL is ideal for motivating with special needs, as well as improving the learning engagement for such individuals. In an inclusive entrepreneurship education setting UDL can be implemented by offering various way students to access information, express their ideas, and engage with the learning process.

Evaluation, Monitoring and Feedback

Regular evaluation and monitoring of inclusive education programmes are essential for measuring their effectiveness and identifying areas of improvement. Engaging in regular feedback can help identify / strength, challenges and areas for improvement in inclusive entrepreneurship education. This helps ensure that strategies and practices being implemented align with the needs and goals of all students.

Overall, inclusive education strategies that integrate entrepreneurship education, foster an entrepreneurship mindset, provide experiential learning opportunities and address

barriers and disparities can effectively stimulate entrepreneurial intentions and contribute to the achievement of sustainable development goals which can be achieved by empowering individuals from diverse background.

Challenges Mitigating against the Successful Implementation of Inclusive Education to Boost Entrepreneurial Intentions

Promoting inclusive education can have a positive impact on various aspects of society, including fostering entrepreneurial intentions among students. However, there are several challenges that can hinder the successful implementation of inclusive education to boost entrepreneurial intentions. Some of these challenges stem from systemic bottleneck, bedeviling our educational system; some of these prominent challenges include;

Lack of Awareness and Understanding

There is an apparent lack of understanding of what inclusive education entails, nor how it can be used to boost entrepreneurial intentions. Adebisi *et al.* (2014) explained that many stakeholders (parents, teachers, policy makers etc) are not in tune with global best practices adopted in inclusive education. This relative lack of awareness can lead to resistance or hesitation when implementing inclusive practices, limiting the potential impact on entrepreneurial development.

Limited Resources

This is a recurrent stumbling block to developmental trends in our educational system. Implementing inclusive education requires adequate resources, specialized training and support systems. Insufficient resources hinder the implementation of inclusive practices and limit the support available for students with diverse needs. This is because additional resources such as specialized teaching methods, assistive technologies and accessible infrastructure are expensive and may not be readily available when there is a paucity of resources. Consequently, it becomes difficult to effectively nurture entrepreneurial intentions among all students, irrespective of background or diverse needs.

Curriculum Rigidity

To foster paradigm changes in pedagogy, there is need for a more dynamic curriculum to be implemented at all levels of our educational system. Inclusive education requires a flexible curriculum and personalized teaching strategies to accommodate different learning styles, abilities and strengths. However, it requires expertise to adapt curricular contents to reflect entrepreneurial intentions.

Stigmatisation and Discrimination

Social stigmas and discrimination against people with disabilities or those from disadvantaged groups can hinder their participation in inclusive educational programmes and discourage their entrepreneurial ambitions.

Cultural and Linguistic Diversity

Addressing the needs of students from diverse cultural and linguistic background requires specialized approaches and resources. The gap created by these barriers are often inimical to a successful practice of inclusive education.

Systemic Barriers

Inclusive education requires systemic changes in policies, legislation and governance structures. However, bureaucratic hurdles, lack of coordination among stakeholders and resistance to change can impede the implementation of inclusive practices. Overcoming these systemic barriers requires strong leadership, advocacy and collaboration among policy makers, educators and community organisations.

Conclusion

Unemployment is a real problem in Nigeria. Several efforts by successive governments to curtail this malady has yielded no tangible result. Therefore, a surge in crime and restiveness among young Nigerians seems to be a direct effect of this. Entrepreneurship has been heralded as a tangible solution as it take millions of young people out of the streets placing them in positions where they can create value and solutions to problems. To engender entrepreneurship, it is vital to nurse an individual's entrepreneurial intentions. Through entrepreneurship education attitudes, aptitudes and skills are imparted in the students boosting their intentions to be innovative and create value.

Unfortunately, several young people struggle to benefit from entrepreneurship education because of their peculiarities caused by physical or mental disability as well as a disadvantaged socio-economic background. Inclusive education was suggested as a veritable strategy for carrying young learners along irrespective of their diverse needs. Several strategies were reviewed as possible ways of implementing inclusive education to boost entrepreneurial intentions. This would ensure that we meet the 2030 SDGs that are currently regarded as the hallmarks of a nation's social and economic progress.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made;

1. There is need for increased advocacy for policy reforms. Policy makers should prioritise incorporating an entrepreneurship focused curriculum into our education policies.
2. Government needs to partner with the organized private financial sector to create financial access to young entrepreneurs irrespective of their background or disabilities. Financial inclusion should be considered an offshoot of inclusive education if entrepreneurial intentions is to be nurtured.
3. Adoption of real-life models will also go a long way in motivating intending entrepreneurs. It is vital that successful individuals they can relate to are invited at intervals to offer inspirational speeches and pep talks.
4. Stringent steps must be taken to dispel stereotypes and prejudices. Awareness should be raised to challenge societal stereotypes surrounding individuals with disabilities or from marginalized communities
5. Social support is vital for vulnerable learners if they are to internalize the benefits of inclusive education. Teachers, school administrators and parents should create supportive ecosystems. This will bode well for the entrepreneurial intentions of the students, as well as their socio-emotional wellbeing in the face of several mitigating personal factors.

References

- Adebisi, R. O., Jerry, J. E., Rasaki, S. A., and Igwe, E. N. (2014). Barriers to special needs education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(11), 451 – 462.
- Adesunkammi, S. O. and Oyolola, S. J. (2023). Formal entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention of female students in Nigerian universities. *East African Journal of Business and Economics*, 6(1), 22 – 33. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajbe.6.1.1068>.
- Alamu, O. (2017). Sustainable development goals in Nigeria: What role(s) for Nigeria's indigenous languages. *European Journal of Research and Reflection Educational Sciences*, 5(4), 1 – 13.
- Ametepey, S. O., Aigbavbola, C. O., Ansah, S. K., Gyadu-Asiedu, W. and Apiaah, L. B. (2023). Meaning, evolution, principles and future of sustainable development: A systematic review. *Sustainability*, 15(1), 1 – 24.
- Channels. News Production (2023). Nigeria's unemployment rate to rise to 41% in 2023-KPMG. Retrieved from <https://www.channelstv.com/2023/04/11/nigerias-unemployment-rate-to-rise-to-41-in-2023-kpmg/>.
- Dalton, E. M. (2017). Beyond universal learning: Guiding principles to reduce barriers in digital & media literacy competence. *Journal of Media Literacy Education*, 9 (2), 17 – 29
- Dare, E. O. and Dare, E. A. (2018). Inclusive quality education for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Sky Journal of Educational Research*, 6(2), 27 – 33.
- Egbewole, I. K. and Lamidi, K. O. (2021). Effect of youth unemployment on the rate of crime in Nigeria: A study of DSTV viewing centres in two local government Areas in Nigeria. *Economic Series*, 20(3), 109 – 127. <https://doi.org/10.26458/2135>.
- Ezeh, P. C. and Nkamnebe, A. D. (2019). Entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduate students in Northern Nigeria: A comparison of two major ethnicities. *UNIZIK Journal of Business*, 2(2), 54 – 63.
- Ezeonwumelu, V.U., and Okoro, C.C. (2021). A dynamic curriculum for functional education in Nigeria. Some lessons from COVID 19 and implications for entrepreneurial self-efficacy. In Unachukwu, G.C. (Eds). *Changing landscape in Educational practices* (pp 482-489). Timex Publishers.
- Kusimo, A. O. and Chidozie, F. C. (2019). Inclusive education and sustainable development goals: A study of the physically challenged in Nigeria. In (ed), Emmanuel O. Amoo, *Covenant University Discourse on Sustainable Development*. *Cogent Social Sciences*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2019.1684175>.
- Law, K. and Breznik, K. (2016). Impacts of innovativeness and attitude on entrepreneurial intentions: among engineering and non-engineering students. *International journal of Technology and Design Education*, 1(2), 1 – 19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-016-9373-0>.
- Magni, F., and Mazzini, A. (2018). Collaboration and entrepreneurship education: requirements and perspective. In: Bosio, G., Minola, T., Origo, F., Tomelleri, S. (eds). *Rethinking entrepreneurial human capital. Studies on Entrepreneurship Structural Change and Industrial Dynamics*. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-90548-8-5>.

- Mensha, J. (2019). Sustainable development: meaning, history, principles, pillars and implications for human action: Literature Review. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1 – 21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331886.2019.1663531>.
- Motta, V. F. and Galina, S. V. R. (2023). Experiential learning in entrepreneurship education: A systematic literature review. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 121 (4), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103919>
- Nelson, J., and Ayawei, M. J. (2020). Effect of corruption on employment in Nigerian empirical investigations. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 8(3), 32 – 46.
- Nkuda, M. O. (2021). Entrepreneurship and economic diversification Nigeria. The moderating influence of enabling environmental on global staelite mobile village's experience. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 3(1), 1 – 25. <https://doi.org/10.33094/26410265.2021.31./25>
- Nzegbulem, P. S. C. and Odionye, E. A. (2016). Management of entrepreneurial education in Nigeria schools: A challenge to educational administrators. *International Journal of Academia*, 2(1), 1 – 13
- Obi, F. B. and Mary, A. (2016). Inclusive education in Nigeria: Access and equity. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(5), 168 – 171.
- Olufemi, A. (2020). Entrepreneurship: An option to solving unemployment problem among Nigeria youths. *European Business & Management*, 6(6), 151- 163. <https://doi.org/10.1168/j.ebm.20200606.14>
- Onyekwelu, P. N., Ibe, G. I., Monyei, F. E., Attamah, J. I. and Ukpere, W. I. (2023). The impact of entrepreneurship institutions on access to micro-financing for sustainable enterprise in an emerging economy. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 1 – 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097425>
- Orji, K. E. and Job, M. (2013). The role of education in national development: Nigerian experience. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(28), 312 – 320.
- Osuji, A. O., Ekhamheye, S. and Tony-Okolo, C. N. (2021). Youth unemployment and restiveness: The Nigerian story. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies*, 3(1), 95 – 104.
- Pimpay, N. (2021). Overcoming gender gaps in entrepreneurship education and training. *Frontier in Education* 6 (1), 1 -10 <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.774876>.
- Tang, Y. (2014). Study framework on integration method of entrepreneurship education and mechanical specialty education for college student. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 2(2), 15 – 19 <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.tecs.20170202.12>
- Wada, E. O. (2018). Unemployment, poverty and corruption in Nigeria. *Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Subjects*, 12(1), 620 – 632.

